

Hexa-Coordinated Complexes of Phenyl (methyl/benzyl) Tin dichlorides with Nitrogen donors

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Studies of Phenyl-methyl-tin dichloride, Phenyl-benzyl-tin dichloride and their coordination compounds with nitrogen donors such as pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline, α -, β -, γ -picolines, morpholine, piperidine and aniline have been undertaken. All these adducts are white solids insensitive to moisture. They have been characterised from their I.R. data mostly in the region $650\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and molar conductance values in nitrobenzene at 25° and their structures discussed.

Lewis acid character of diorganotin dichlorides, R_2SnCl_2 , (where $R = CH_3, C_2H_5, n\text{-}C_3H_7, n\text{-}C_4H_9$ or C_6H_5) have been studied extensively during the past few years¹⁻⁵. But no attempts have been made with compounds having different organic groups. This work has been selected for the present communication. The compounds RR_1SnCl_2 with $R =$ phenyl and $R_1 =$ alkyl or aralkyl have been prepared and their adducts with primary, secondary and tertiary amines studied. Studies of their I.R. spectra in the $4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region and molar conductance in nitrobenzene at 25° have been carried out.

EXPERIMENTAL

Triphenyl methyl tin (m.p. $60^\circ\text{--}61^\circ$) and triphenyl benzyl tin (m.p. 90°) were prepared respectively by the methods of Kraus and Schmitz⁶ and Kipping⁷ modified by Jaura *et al.*⁸.

Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed for half an hour through their refluxing benzene solutions. The resulting solid products were freed from benzene by distillation and crystallised twice from petroleum ether to give phenyl-methyl-tin dichloride (m.p. 43°) and phenyl-benzyl-tin dichloride (m.p. 84°).

Amines purified by distillation were made to react with organotin chloride solution in petroleum ether. The solid products obtained on chilling were filtered and dried under vacuum.

The tin contents of the adducts were estimated gravimetrically as SnO_2 and the halogen contents by Vohlard's method.

I.R. spectra in the $4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region were recorded in KBr disc.

Molar conductance values were determined from the specific conductances of $10^{-3}M$ solutions of the adducts in nitrobenzene at 25° using Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Phenyl-methyl-tin dichloride and phenyl-benzyl-tin dichloride have been found to form 1 : 2 (acid : base) adducts with pyridine, quinoline, isoquinoline, α , β , and γ -picolines, morpholine, piperidine and aniline. They are all white solids and quite stable in air. The analytical and other data of the adducts are given in Tables 1 and 2.

I.R. Spectra : The donation of electrons through the nitrogen atom of pyridine and other tertiary nitrogen bases are expected to cause an appreciable shift associated with C = C and C = N stretching frequencies in the 1600–650 cm^{-1} region^{9,10} but the spectra are too complicated in this region due to the overlapping of C = C and C–H stretching frequencies of the phenyl group of organotin halide with those of the ligands.

In conformity with the earlier observation¹¹, N–H stretching frequencies in case of morpholine, piperidine and aniline adducts record a considerable fall due to the weakening of N–H bond on coordination (Table 3). The spectra of the adducts show broad bands which may probably be due to the overlapping C–H and N–H vibrations.

Frequencies below 650 cm^{-1} may tentatively be assigned to the ligand or vibrations around tin atom.

It has been reported¹² that the lowest ring vibrations of pyridine at 605 cm^{-1} (out of plane ring deformation) and at 405 cm^{-1} (in plane ring deformation) are most sensitive to the substituents on the tin atom and increase on coordination. I.R. Spectrum in case of $\text{Ph}(\text{CH}_3)\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Py}$ shows two peaks at 630 cm^{-1} and 420 cm^{-1} and in case of $\text{Ph}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Py}$ at 628 cm^{-1} and 425 cm^{-1} . These peaks thus appear to be corresponding to the above ring vibrations.

Sn–C stretching frequencies in case of organotin halides are dependent upon the effective nuclear charge on the tin atom¹⁴. In organotin chlorides except for Sn–Ph absorption bands, which appear in the region 250–300 cm^{-1} , Sn–alkyl (where alkyl = CH_3 , C_2H_5 , $n\text{-C}_3\text{H}_7$, $n\text{-C}_4\text{H}_9$) stretching frequencies have been reported to fall in the region 500–600 cm^{-1} .^{3,13,14,15} In accordance with the observation of Poller¹ and Srivastava¹⁶, a strong band at 255 cm^{-1} and a doublet at 260 cm^{-1} and 250 cm^{-1} in the spectra of $\text{Ph}(\text{CH}_3)\text{SnCl}_2$ and $\text{Ph}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_2$ respectively may be assigned to Sn–Ph stretching frequencies. Another strong band appearing at 545 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $\text{Ph}(\text{CH}_3)\text{SnCl}_2$ has been assigned to Sn– CH_3 stretching frequency. In the spectrum of $\text{Ph}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_2$, if $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$ group be treated as CH_3 group in which one H atom has been substituted by a phenyl group, the Sn– $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$ stretching frequency would be expected to fall considerably below 545 cm^{-1} . Some absorption bands in the region 400–300 cm^{-1} have been observed in the spectrum of $\text{Ph}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_2$ and those of its adducts. Sn– $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2$ may probably be regarded to fall in the same region but there is no evidence to support this view. Sn–Ph and Sn– CH_3 stretching frequencies appear to remain almost unchanged on coordination. This is in agreement with the observation of earlier workers also^{1,17,18}.

Sn–Cl stretching frequencies of organotin chlorides, which are dependent upon the degree of alkylation of the tin atom, generally decrease in magnitude with the increasing

degree of alkylation¹⁴. In case of diorganotin dichlorides the Sn-Cl stretching frequencies have been reported to fall in the region 360–300 cm^{-1} .^{13–15} In the spectrum of $\text{Ph}(\text{CH}_3)\text{SnCl}_2$ the bands appearing at 340 cm^{-1} , 320 cm^{-1} and in the spectrum of $\text{Ph}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}_2)\text{SnCl}_2$ at 332 cm^{-1} , 320 cm^{-1} and 302 cm^{-1} may be assigned to Sn-Cl stretching frequencies. On coordination with amines through nitrogen, the positive charge on tin atom would decrease and subsequently Sn-Cl bond length would increase resulting in a considerable fall in the Sn-Cl stretching frequencies so that they may appear in the region 250–200 cm^{-1} . Out of all the adducts undertaken only those marked (*) in Table 4 and 5 have been scanned in the region 250–200 cm^{-1} . Specific assignments even in these cases being difficult the bands appearing only in the region 200–220 cm^{-1} have been assigned to Sn-Cl stretching frequencies and those appearing below 220 cm^{-1} have been left unassigned. These may include some due to Sn←N frequencies which are expected to fall in the region below 220 cm^{-1} on coordination^{13,14,19} or these may be due to the overlapping of both the Sn-Cl and Sn-N frequencies.

Structural Inferences : In all the adducts where tin has been found to exist in the hexacoordination state, octahedral structure is expected. Sn-C, Sn-Cl and Sn-N stretching frequencies which can be helpful in deciding the position of the organic groups, chlorines and ligands around tin atom, do not lead to any positive conclusion. However, in those cases where the spectra have been recorded in the region 250–200 cm^{-1} (Table 4 & 5) and the Sn-Cl stretching frequencies assigned with in this region, the appearance of two or more than two bands suggest that the chlorines are in the cis-position in the molecules. Due to the difference in nature and the size of the organic groups, the Sn-C stretching frequencies in the present case are not helpful in assigning the position to the organic groups. However by analogy with the observation of Beattie³ in case of $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Py}$ and Poller¹⁷ in case of $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Py}$ where they have proposed that the organic groups are in the trans-position, and keeping in view the larger size of the organic groups leading to greater steric and the intergroups repulsions in the present case, the organic groups are more likely to be present in the trans position. In view of this explanation, these adducts may be proposed to have a structure in general as

Where R = Phenyl
R¹ = methyl or benzyl

But in those cases where the ligands are of larger size than the organic groups, these repulsions would be far greater. In such cases, therefore, the structure may be assigned as.

In case of the morpholine adducts only one Sn-Cl stretching frequency appears to be infrared active on coordination. The chlorines are thus likely to occupy a linear position¹⁷. The

octahedral structure proposed for the morpholine adducts may be represented as

Molar Conductance Measurements : Molar conductance values at 25° of the adducts which are reasonably soluble in nitrobenzene have been studied. They fall mainly in the region 1–10 cm² ohm⁻¹ mole⁻¹ which classify them as non-electrolytes. The conductance

TABLE 1
Analytical data for the adducts of Ph(CH₃)SnCl₂ with Amines

Adduct	m.p. °C	Λ	% of Chlorine		% of tin	
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
Ph (CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2L ₁	147	7.21	15.67	16.13	26.69	27.04
Ph (CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2L ₂	133	18.32	12.85	13.15	22.56	22.03
Ph (CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2L ₃	133	8.35	13.43	13.15	21.73	22.03
Ph (CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2L ₄	132	8.67	15.21	15.17	25.73	25.43
Ph (CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2L ₅	134	11.82	14.86	15.17	25.09	25.43
Ph (CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2L ₆	141	7.87	14.75	15.17	25.13	25.43
Ph (CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2L ₇	137–38	5.44	16.17	15.57	25.85	26.09
Ph (CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2L ₈	177–19	8.97	16.16	15.70	26.01	26.33
*Ph (CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2L ₉	108	—	14.71	15.17	24.90	25.43

TABLE 2
Analytical data for the adducts of Ph(C₆H₅CH₂)SnCl₂ with Amines

Adduct	m.p. °C	Λ	% of Chlorine		% of tin	
			Found	Reqd.	Found	Reqd.
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2L ₁	112–14	3.50	13.39	13.75	22.72	23.06
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2L ₂	90	4.75	11.86	11.52	19.68	19.32
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2L ₃	120–23	6.40	11.32	11.52	18.97	19.32
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2L ₄	72–75	13.72	12.56	13.05	21.97	21.87
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2L ₅	120–23	6.87	12.95	13.05	21.34	21.87
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2L ₆	88–92	14.20	12.83	13.05	21.50	21.87
*Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2L ₇	133–35	—	13.45	13.34	21.97	22.36
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2L ₈	160–62	3.08	13.19	13.44	22.85	23.15
*Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2L ₉	112–15	—	12.53	13.05	21.35	21.87

(decomposed)

where L₁ = Pyridine, L₂ = Quinoline, L₃ = Isoquinoline, L₄ = α-Picoline, L₅ = β-Picoline, L₆ = γ-Picoline, L₇ = Morpholine, L₈ = Piperidine, L₉ = Aniline. Λ = Molar conductance in cm² ohm⁻¹ mole⁻¹.

* Molar conductance could not be determined because the adducts were insoluble in nitrobenzene.

TABLE 3

N-H stretching frequencies in Morpholine, Piperidine and Aniline adducts (cm⁻¹)

Amine	(N-H)	Adducts	(N-H) & (C-H)
Morpholine	3340s	Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2-Morpholine	3000-2900 s.br.
		Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2-Morpholine	2960-2875 m.br.
Piperidine	3290m	Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2-Piperidine	2870-2830 s.br.
		Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2-Piperidine	—
Aniline	3390m	Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2-Aniline	2850-2750 s.br.
	3315m	Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2-Aniline	3025m
			2975m
			2900m

TABLE 4

I.R. data of Ph(CH₃)SnCl₂ and its adducts with Amines

Compound	$\nu(\text{Sn-Ph})$ cm ⁻¹	$\nu(\text{Sn-CH}_3)$ cm ⁻¹	$\nu(\text{Sn-Cl})$ cm ⁻¹	Unassigned str. fre- quencies (cm ⁻¹)
Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂	255s	545s	340m, 320m	
*Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2 Pyridine	255s	560s	245sh, 220m	210w, 205w, 202m
*Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2 Quinoline	255s	535s	225w, 220m	210w, 205w, 202m
Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2 Isoquinoline	255s	530s	—	—
Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2 α -Picoline	255s	560s	—	—
Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2 β -picoline	255s	530s	—	—
*Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2 γ -picoline	260m	542s	244m, 242m, 228m	202m
*Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2 Morpholine	260m	545m	225m	—
Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2 Piperidine	255s	530m	245sh, 225w, 220m	210w, 205w, 202w
Ph(CH ₃)SnCl ₂ .2 Aniline	260s	560s	—	—

TABLE 5

I.R. data of Ph(C₆H₅CH₂)SnCl₂ and its adducts with Amines

Compound	$\nu(\text{Sn-Ph})$ cm ⁻¹	$\nu(\text{Sn-Cl})$ cm ⁻¹	Unassigned str. frequencies (cm ⁻¹)
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂	260s 250s	332m, 320m, 302w	348m
*Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2 Pyridine	250s	240w, 225m	352m, 212w, 210w, 205w
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2 Quinoline	255s	—	370m, 275w
*Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2 Isoquinoline	255s	245w, 230w, 220w	360m, 212w, 210w
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2 α -picoline	250s	—	370m, 360w, 320s
*Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2 β -picoline	255s	242sh, 225m, 222m	355m, 212w, 205w
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2 γ -picoline	255s	—	—
*Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2 Morpholine	255s	220v.s.	392m, 355w, 330w, 210w, 205w
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2 Piperidine	255s	—	305w, 270w
Ph(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂)SnCl ₂ .2 Aniline	255s	—	375w, 350w

values of the adducts Ph(CH₃)SnCl₂.2 Quinoline, Ph(CH₃)SnCl₂.2 β -picoline, Ph(C₆H₅CH₂)SnCl₂.2 α -picoline, Ph(C₆H₅CH₂)SnCl₂.2 γ -picoline occur generally in the range 10-20 cm² ohm⁻¹ mole⁻¹ (Tables 1 & 2). This indicates that these adducts undergo some dissociation in nitrobenzene²⁰.

REFERENCES

1. R. C. Poller and D. L. B. Toley, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 1578.
2. K. L. Jaura, V. K. Sharma, Kuldip Chander and K. K. Sharma, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 883.
3. I. R. Beattie and G. P. Mequillan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 1519.
4. G. Matsubayashi, T. Tanaka and R. Okawara, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1968, **30**, 1831.
5. K. L. Jaura, Kuldip Chander and K. K. Sharma, *Z. anorg. Chem.* 1970, 375, 303.
6. E. Krause and M. Schmitz, *Ber.*, 1919, **52**, 2150.
7. F. B. Kipping, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2365.
8. K. L. Jaura, L. K. Churamani and K. K. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, **4**, 329.
9. K. L. Jaura, K. C. Jindal and K. K. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 91.
10. R. C. Paul and S. L. Chadha, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, **6**, 272.
11. N. N. Greenwood and K. Wade, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1130.
12. N. S. Gill, R. H. Nuttal, D. E. Saife and D. W. A. Sharp, *J. Inorg. Nuclear. Chem.*, 1961, **18**, 79.
13. (Miss) J. P. Clark and C. J. Wilkins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 871.
14. R. J. H. Clark, A. G. Davies and R. J. Puddephatt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 1828.
15. E. V. Vanden Berghe, L. Verdonck and G. P. Vander Kelen, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1969, **16**, 497.
16. T. S. Srivastava, *J. Organometal. Chem.*, 1969, **16**, 253.
17. R. C. Poller, J. N. R. Ruddick and M. Thevarasa, *J. Chem. Soc.*, (A), 1969, 2327.
18. R. J. H. Clark, and C. S. Williams, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1965, **21**, 1861.
19. T. Tanaka, Y. Matsumura and R. Okawara, Y. Musya and S. Kinumaki, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan* 1968, **41**, 1497.
20. J. E. Fergusson, W. R. Roper and C. J. Wilkins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 3716.